

diseases¹. Nearly thirty members of the genus are available in India, almost all of them are chemically investigated². We report herein a few polyphenolic constituents from *I. mysorensis* Rottl, which is the first report from this species.

The dried leaves of *I. mysorensis* (0.5 kg) (material collected near Tirupati, District Chittoor) were successively extracted with solvents of increasing polarity. The dry acetone extract (15 g) was macerated with dry ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate soluble fraction on chromatographic separation and purification (silica gel G column, benzene-ethyl acetate, 8:2, 6:4, 1:1, 2:8) afforded two crystalline compounds A and B which were found to be phenolic acids, on the basis the uv and ir data. They were identified as (A) protocatechuic acid and (B) *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid by comparison of m.p. and m.m.p. with the authentic samples.

The ethyl acetate insoluble fraction on separation by pc (two-dimensional, Whatman 3 mm, butanol-acetone-water (v/v) 4:1:5, 15% AcOH) and purification yielded two yellow compounds C and D, which by colour reactions and *R_f* data were found to be flavonoid-*O*-glycosides. The uv data of the compounds in methanol and shifts with diagnostic reagents indicated that the sugar units were present in 7- and 3-positions in compounds C and D, respectively.

The products of acid hydrolysis using 7% H₂SO₄ and the difficulty in hydrolysis of compound C showed clearly that the sugar unit was present in 7-position and it was rhamnoglucose. The aglycone was identified as apigenin. Complete methylation of compound C with dimethyl sulphate and K₂CO₃ and subsequent hydrolysis gave an aglycone identified as 5,4'-dimethylapigenin³. Compound C was thus identified as apigenin-7-rhamnoglucoside rhoifolin, which was confirmed by the nmr data of the glycoside.

Compound D underwent easy hydrolysis with 5% H₂SO₄, giving rise to kaempferol and the sugars, rhamnose and glucose. The nmr data of the compound showed that the sugar unit was neohesperidoside⁴. Thus compound D was identified as kaempferol-3-neohesperidoside.

The dried methanol extract on chromatographic separation over a polyamide column and further purification with aqueous methanol (1:1) eluent yielded an orange-red compound E. The chromatographic and uv data indicated that the compound was a flavone-*O*-glycoside, and was identified as apigenin-7,4'-diglucoside depending on the products of acid hydrolysis (apigenin and glucose) and comparison of the *R_f* data in different solvent systems⁵.

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Complexation of Silver(I) with Morpholinylthiocarbonyl Acid Amide and its Use as an Amperometric Reagent for Trace Determination of Silver(I)

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THE present work reports an analytical and ir spectral examination of Ag^I complex with morpholinylthiocarbonyl acid amide (MTA). Based on the complexation of Ag^I with MTA, an amperometric method for the determination of traces of silver has also been developed.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand, (4-morpholinyl)thiocarbonyl acid amide (MTA) was prepared by the reported method¹. The crude product was purified by recrystallisation from ethanol (Found: C, 41.2; H, 6.81; N, 19.19; S, 21.85. C₅H₁₀N₂O₃ calcd. for: C, 41.09; H, 6.84; N, 19.17; S, 21.91%).

Ag^I MTA complex: To a cold aqueous solution of ligand (1 mmol) an aqueous solution of silver nitrate (1 mmol) was added with constant stirring, and the resulting white precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered and washed thoroughly with distilled water and finally dried in vacuum (Found: Ag, 53.15; C, 19.00; H, 3.20; N, 8.73; S, 10.18. Calcd. for: Ag, 53.17; C, 18.99; H, 3.16; N, 8.86; S, 10.13%).

The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 grating infrared spectrophotometer in the range 4 000-650 cm⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

Ir bands due to ν_{NH} (3 410-3 200 cm⁻¹) in ligand show decrease in intensity and broadening

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in the complex ($3\,400\text{--}3\,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which is an indication of coordination through nitrogen². Shifting of $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ (from $2\,960$ in ligand to $2\,920\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complex) towards lower frequency and broadening show complexation with silver. The shifting of NH_2 deformation vibration ($1\,620\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the ligand towards lower frequency ($1\,610\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complex, supports metal to ligand bonding through nitrogen.

The broadening of thioamide I band (at $1\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand) in the Ag^{I} -complex indicates bonding through nitrogen. A slight decrease in frequency and intensity of thioamide II band (near $1\,345\text{--}1\,310\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand) in the spectrum of complex is observed. In thioamide III band involving mainly $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ ($1\,060$ and $1\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in ligand), reduced band intensity and lowered wave number on complexation indicate sulphur bonding³.

The mixed H-N-C=S band due to C-N antisymmetric stretching and N-H deformation near $1\,270\text{--}1\,260\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand shifted by 10 cm^{-1} ($1\,260\text{--}1\,250\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in complex with reduced intensity. A sharp band which appears at $2\,100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is an indication of M-SCN type of bonding in the complex^{4,5}. No change of the bands at $1\,180\text{--}1\,100\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are due to ring C-N-C and C-O-C of morpholine, showed non-involvement of morpholine ring nitrogen or oxygen in coordination⁶.

Amperometric titration of Ag^{I} with MTA: Solutions containing varying amount of silver ($0.05\text{--}10\text{ mg ml}^{-1}$ of solution) in 0.1 M potassium nitrate adjusted to $\text{pH } 2.86$ were amperometrically titrated with morpholinylthiocarbonyl acid amide (MTA) solution (0.01 M) using a manually operated polarograph with multiflex galvanometer (sensitivity $8.10 \times 10^{-9}\text{ A/div.}$). A dropping mercury electrode was used as an indicator electrode and mercury pool as the reference. The capillary used for the dropping mercury electrode had a m value of 2.373 mg s^{-1} at a drop time of 3.0 s in air-free 0.1 M potassium nitrate at 35 cm effective height of mercury column ($m^{2/3} t^{1/3} = 2.136\text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{ s}^{-1/3}$). A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurement. All the measurements were made at room temperature ($27 \pm 0.5^\circ$). The current-voltage curves for Ag and MTA were separately recorded in 0.1 M potassium nitrate at $\text{pH } 2.86$. The titrations were performed at an applied voltage of -0.1 V vs Hg pool, the plateau potential of silver wave at which MTA remained unaffected (Fig. 2). The current-voltage behaviour of silver and MTA in 0.1 M potassium nitrate ($\text{pH}=2.86$) and at ionic strength 0.1 M (KNO_3) gave well defined cathodic reduction wave for Ag^{I} . The height of the diffusion current was proportional to silver concentration.

On titrating each of the experimental sets (containing varying known amounts of Ag^{I} , separately) at the applied voltage -0.1 V with MTA (at $\text{pH}=2.86$), a white precipitate was obtained. The plot of galvanometer deflection, after necessary

Fig. 1. Amperometric titration curve of Ag^{I} with MTA concn. of Ag^{I} : (A) 0.01 and (B) $0.02\text{ mM}/10\text{ ml}$; concn. of MTA = $0.01\text{ mM}/10\text{ ml}$.

volume correction against the volume of MTA added, yielded L-shaped curve (Fig. 1). The endpoint indicated a metal to ligand ratio of $1:1$, which was in good agreement with the elemental analysis of the isolated $\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}\text{-MTA}$ complex.

Fig. 2. Current-voltage curves in 0.5 M KNO_3 ($\text{pH}=2.86$); (a) $2\text{ mM Ag}^{\text{I}}$ and (L) 1 mM MTA .

The minimum quantity ($0.05\text{ mg}/10\text{ ml}$ of analyte) of silver could be successfully determined by this procedure, with less than $\pm 0.9\%$ error and standard deviation of less than 0.1% .

Diverse ion effect: The above titration was performed in presence of known amounts of foreign ions. The titrations were not hampered by the presence of a large number of foreign ions (mg): NH_4^+ (50), Na^+ (115), Ca^{2+} (25), Ba^{2+} (25), Al^{3+} (30), nitrate (120) and acetate (50). However, small amounts of Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , chloride, bromide and iodide seriously interfered.

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A New Potentiometric Method for the Sequential Titration of Permanganate and Vanadate with Sodium Oxalate at Room Temperature using Photochemical Reduction of Ferric Oxalate

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Experimental

STOCK solutions of vanadate, permanganate and sodium oxalate were prepared by the usual procedures¹.

A Philips high pressure mercury vapour lamp (Repro lamp) with a power consumption of 125 W was used for irradiating the titration mixture. A sensitive potentiometric setup consisting of a Toshniwal PL 52 portable potentiometer with a built in galvanometer was used in all potentiometric titrations. A bright platinum rod immersed in titration mixture and a saturated calomel half-cell were used as indicator and reference electrodes, respectively. The two cells are connected through a saturated ammonium nitrate solution salt-bridge.

Recommended procedure for the determination of permanganate and vanadate in mixtures: To different aliquots of 0.05 N permanganate or vana-

date or their mixtures solutions were added 0.05 M Fe^{III} solution (5.0 ml) and sufficient 20 N H_2SO_4 to keep the overall acidity at 1 N. The mixture was diluted with distilled water to 50 ml. The beaker was exposed under the light from a Repro lamp with its contents and then titrated with 0.05 M sodium oxalate solution potentiometrically keeping the overall titration period around 20 min under exposure to the light. The contents were stirred constantly with a magnetic stirrer. The variation in potentials of the system was followed for each aliquot of sodium oxalate added by potentiometric method.

Results and Discussion

When the solutions of permanganate and vanadate are individually titrated with sodium oxalate in presence of Fe^{III} , the Fe^{II} ions formed *in situ* due to the photochemical reduction of ferric oxalate is found to reduce Mn^{VII} to Mn^{II} and V^V to V^{IV} which can be followed potentiometrically. In this process, Fe^{III} is regenerated. The concentration of Fe^{III} is found to be not critical and if a minimum of Fe^{III} is maintained the titration can be effectively followed. However, in the complete absence of Fe^{III} the titrations can not be performed. Due to good differences in the redox potentials of $\text{Mn}^{VII}/\text{Mn}^{II}$ and V^V/V^{IV} systems from that of $\text{Fe}^{III}/\text{Fe}^{II}$ when all the oxidant is reduced completely, the indicator electrode responds to the later system resulting in large decrease in the potentials observed as end-point is reached.

The investigations revealed that these titrations can be best carried out in between 0.5 and 3.0 N acid medium with respect to sulphuric acid with 20 min time to complete the titration under exposure to light.

The same procedure can also be extended to titrate mixtures of permanganate and vanadate. In the titration of permanganate, vanadate mixtures with oxalate in presence of Fe^{III} variation in potentials of the system (Fig. 1) with increasing concentration of oxalate showed two breaks, the one corresponding to the complete reduction of permanganate (1 060–840 mV) and the second corresponding to the complete reduction of vanadate (980–530 mV).

To test the quantitative nature of the titrations of the mixtures of permanganate and vanadate, a large number of determinations are made with varying concentrations of permanganate and vanadate (in the range 0.05–0.30) which gave reproducible results with standard deviation in the range 0.003–0.005.

Reaction mechanism: When these oxidants are titrated with oxalate in presence of Fe^{III} under exposure to light, Fe^{III} will be preferentially reacting with oxalate added and may be undergoing